

INFLUENCE OF QUALITY OF WEB-BASED LIBRARY SERVICE AND LIBRARIANS' BEHAVIORAL PERFORMANCE ON STUDENTS' E-LOYALTY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195639>

ABSTRACT

The advancement in the digital world particularly in academic and research libraries has redefined information access and reshaped librarians' roles in delivering services and cultivating e-loyalty among users. This study explored the connection of quality of web-based library service, librarians' behavioral performance, and students' e-loyalty. The study utilized the descriptive correlational research design to determine the quality of web-based library services and librarians' behavioral performance and its influence on students' e-loyalty. Random sampling method was employed six hundred fifty-seven (657) graduate students from the different schools in Northern Mindanao participated in the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze and interpret the data. The study revealed that the quality of web-based library service was very satisfactory with delivery, environmental, and outcome factors having the highest means. Moreover, the librarians' behavioral performance was high in the areas of inclusion, approachability, and evaluation, except in the search process which was rated the lowest. The quality of web-based library service and librarians' behavioral performance significantly influence graduate students' e-loyalty to school web-based library service. Accordingly, the quality of web-based library services and the positive behaviors of librarians influence the students' e-loyalty. It is recommended that future researchers may consider exploring other variables related to the quality of web-based library services such as e-trust, e-satisfaction, electronic word of mouth, and continuation intention that could potentially influence school web-based E-loyalty of students.

KEYWORDS: *Quality of web-based library service, librarians' behavioral performance, Student E-loyalty*

INTRODUCTION

Academic and research libraries have rapidly adapted to the digital world, extending their reach and Academic and research libraries have rapidly adapted to the digital world, extending their reach and ensuring quality services for user satisfaction. These libraries have consistently applied web-based library services such as access to digitized materials, online databases, web OPAC, online help, and virtual reference services in order to satisfy the information needs of the library users. Because of these applications, it redefined information access and reshaped librarians' roles in delivering services and cultivating e-loyalty among users.

Kumar (2023) contends that while developing and deploying web-based services, libraries need to be conscious of these constraints and take action to overcome them. A thorough research, therefore, is imperative to better understand how these web-based library services are continuously used once they are adopted in order to support the effectiveness of digital learning materials (Misra, 2023). Seemingly, with the adversity of today's digital environment, there is limited literature emphasizing that maintaining customer loyalty is a major challenge for librarians (Haruna and Tahira, 2015).

Such adoption of these web-based library services is accounted for e-loyalty. E-loyalty, or "E-Loy," is the term used to describe a web-based consumer positive attitude and assertiveness toward online vendors, merchants, or sellers, which results in continuous or repeated purchases regularly (Al-Adwan A.S & Al-Horani, 2019). Numerous factors positively influence e-loyalty as identified in some literature. This includes perceived value (Rahi & Abd Ghani, 2016), satisfaction (López and Vázquez, 2017) website security (Cui et al., 2018), and trust (Giao et al., 2020). Each of these factors has been thoroughly examined and found to have a major influence on the development of e-loyalty, thereby, making web-based library service users in the future to be more loyal toward e-service quality providers (Muhammad, 2023).

Conversely, web-based library service face various challenges related to accuracy, authenticity, readability, copyright and intellectual property rights, accessibility, user comfort, technical barriers, digital divide, and security, among other issues (Ilahi et al., 2019; Marino, 2018; Saini, 2017; Sharma, 2018). These deficiencies need to be address to ensure the quality service and efficient provision of web-based services and to ensure a positive user experience. On another view, limited attention has been given in the literature in terms of understanding how the quality of web-library services and librarians' behavior influence graduate students' e-loyalty. Investigating this influence is crucial for understanding how web service quality and librarian behavior influence students' e-loyalty. This theoretical research gap aligns with the findings of Dhaigude et al. (2023), emphasizing the significance of perceived value and satisfaction in shaping e-loyalty within online contexts. Therefore, exploring the influence of graduate students' e-loyalty in educational settings in Northern Mindanao would enrich theoretical frameworks and provide practical insights for enhancing student e-loyalty towards web-based library services.

Thus, the significance of e-loyalty is increasing which necessitates a deeper understanding of the relationship between web-based library services quality and librarians' behavioral performance, especially in Northern Mindanao, where the said library services are being introduced.

Concomitant to this, the researcher explored the connections between the quality of web-based library service and the behavioral performance of librarians including the potential interrelationships between service quality, librarian behavior, and student e-loyalty. This study hoped to provide valuable insights and recommendations for libraries in Northern Mindanao. These libraries are striving to thrive in the digital age while fostering lasting connections and networks among fellow librarians. Simultaneously, they are also considering unique challenges and opportunities, as they tried to develop a comprehensive theoretical model that elucidates the interrelationships between service quality, librarian behavior, and e-loyalty among library users.

Framework

This study hypothesized that the quality of web-based library services and librarians' behavioral performance influence student's e-loyalty. This means that students who experience high level of quality of web-based services in terms of environmental factors, delivery factors, and outcome factors along with exceptional librarians' behavioral performance significantly increase their level of e-loyalty towards the schools' web-based library service.

This study investigated the relationship between the quality of web-based library services, librarians' behavioral performance, and student e-loyalty. This study was anchored on the Equity Theory (Adams and Freedman, 1963), which explores the psychological aspects of fairness and equity in exchanges. This framework aimed to understand how perceived fairness and quality influence student loyalty in the context of digital library services.

The Equity Theory posits that individuals are motivated when they perceive fairness in the rewards they receive relative to their contributions and those of others (Adams, 1963). This theory has been widely applied in organizational and business contexts as it encompasses the ability to attract and retain customers. This ability hinges on an organization's capacity to enhance the value of its products and to meet and surpass customer expectations (Kegoro & Justus, 2020).

In the context of web-based library services, this framework suggests that when students perceive web-based library services as high in quality in terms of environmental factors, delivery factors, and outcome factors, they are more likely to develop e-loyalty. E-loyalty here refers to the sustained commitment and preference of students towards utilizing web-based library resources and services.

Web-based library services encompass the efforts and resources invested by the library in providing a range of digitally delivered services such as access to digitized materials, online databases, Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC), virtual reference services, and

online help. These web-based library services, as proposed by Kiran and Diljit (2012), are evaluated based on environmental, delivery, and outcome factors to ensure they meet or exceed user expectations.

Environmental Factors. This dimension encompasses elements like website design, accessibility, responsiveness, and the efficiency of search functionalities. When these factors are well-optimized, users can easily navigate the digital library, find relevant resources, and access resources seamlessly. Similarly, Aba et al., (2017) identified that insufficiencies in computer technology infrastructure, inconsistent access to electricity, limited proficiency of librarians in computer technology, insufficient Internet bandwidth, among other factors, are the primary obstacles influencing the provision of services to students in university libraries in the northern central region of Nigeria.

For instance, environmental factors also consider remote access to e-resources from any location. Remote access facilities ensure optimum usage of library resources on the university campus and beyond library hours and allow researchers easy access to quality resources around the clock. Thus, it allows library patrons to search holdings of the library's catalogue and other locally developed library contents such as digitized collections along with all the information resources subscribed by the library from a single search interface (Comeaux, 2017).

Delivery Factors. Delivery Factor emphasizes the various elements and features that go into giving users access to materials and services via online library platforms. This factor is crucial in ensuring the quality of web-based library services. Opoko and Kwaku (2022) stressed that the web-based library services are influenced by the following delivery factors such as perceived ease-of-use and perceived usefulness, service functionality and task functionality. The availability of online materials of web-based library services also plays a significant role in determining the quality-of-service delivery.

Outcome Factor. Another contributing factor affecting the quality of web-based library service is the outcome factor. This factor refers to the effectiveness of the library in meeting users' information needs, including the availability of up-to-date and comprehensive content, and timely response of the librarians. Sahu (2007) asserted that if a library delivers accurate information to the correct user within an appropriate framework and in a timely manner, it can be deemed as offering high-quality service to its users. A recent study conducted by Lawal and Kannan (2021) revealed that outcome factors contribute to the underutilization of the library. These factors include subpar internet connectivity, frequent power outages, the absence of up-to-date awareness services for both physical and digital resources, and an inadequately conducive environment.

Librarian's behavioral performance. It encompasses the efforts and interactions of librarians in assisting students, providing support, and enhancing user experience in the online environment. The behavioral performance of librarians plays a crucial role in shaping student perceptions and e-loyalty such as inclusion, approachability, engagement, searching, evaluation, and closure (RUSA Guidelines for Behavioral

Performance Reference and Information Service Providers, 2023). Positive librarian behaviors are expected to enhance service quality perceptions and subsequently influence e-loyalty. The components of these e-loyalty are discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

Inclusion. In the librarians' behavioral performance, it is about ensuring that libraries and its services and resources are welcoming and accessible to all members of the community. It involves a commitment to diversity, cultural sensitivity, accessibility, and outreach efforts to provide relevant and equitable services to everyone, regardless of their background or circumstances closure (RUSA Guidelines for Behavioral Performance Reference and Information Service Providers, 2023). **Approachability.** One of the critical aspects of excelling in delivering library services, whether in virtual or online settings, is to exhibit an exceptional level of approachability. Bonnet and McAlexander (2016) found that providing approachable assistance by library personnel to students is crucial for delivering services effectively and creating a favorable impression during online library transactions. Schwartz and colleagues (2014) stressed the importance of librarians being prepared and responsive when handling chat inquiries. They suggested that chat providers respond to questions within a minute to ensure patrons experience at sufficient time. Additionally, they recommended greeting chat users with a welcome message as they enter the chat system. When a chat provider is assisting another patron, it is advisable to acknowledge the waiting patron. However, if the inquiry is a simple directional or quick reference question, remote patrons can assist. RUSA Guidelines for Behavioral Performance Reference and Information Service Providers, (2023) recommends that librarians offer clear and understandable web links to all reference services to avoid technical jargons.

Another behavioral performance of librarians that needs to be considered in terms of catering to library users in web-based queries and concerns is their extent of engagement towards library users. Engagement behaviors require the librarian to firmly commit to delivering practical information assistance. In the context of online chat, maintaining a sense of interest can be challenging. According to RUSA Guidelines for Behavioral Performance Reference and Information Service Providers (2023) keeping the conversation going with patrons is advisable. In an email-based environment, responding promptly to all inquiries is essential. With this, it is crucial to make reference policies and procedures and should be made accessible on the library's website. This transparency helps patrons understand the types of questions they can ask during a chat session and the responses they can expect within a specified timeframe.

Searching is another vital behavior that librarians should possess and practice in retrieving information needs of library patrons. Librarians should be knowledgeable about search strategies and clarify steps for patrons while respecting their time constraints. They should collaborate with patrons in selecting appropriate search terms, inquire about additional terms, and provide search tips to empower them to find answers to similar questions in the future. In remote settings, librarians should use suitable technology to ensure efficient search methods (e.g., co-browsing, scanning, faxing) and to facilitate the search process (RUSA, 2023).

Evaluation is a widely used method to measure the effectiveness of any organization, including libraries. This holds for web-based libraries as well. Sinhababu & Kumar, (2019) highlighted that gathering regular feedback from staff and users is essential to assess the efficiency and effectiveness of the library services. This feedback plays a crucial role in ensuring the delivery of high-quality services. Librarians as experts in evaluating the quality of information considered factors like accuracy, authority, bias, comprehensiveness, and coverage in the evaluative process. The ultimate goal of this process is to meet students' reference and information needs, whether in-person or virtual (RUSA, 2023).

Closure. To make sure that the user's information demands are satisfied, closure is essential. Librarians should follow up with patrons after they leave the desk to see if their inquiries have been addressed and urge them to visit the reference desk again or make use of other resources, such as chat reference. Following up with reference interviews using techniques like roving is crucial. Hirko and Ross (2004) emphasized the importance of roving as it gave opportunities for librarians to ask users about their satisfaction with services, addressing concerns, expressing gratitude, and promoting ongoing service utilization.

In line with this, the study explored the implications of this relationship on students' e-loyalty, hypothesizing that a positive user experience resulting from high-quality satisfaction of web-based library services and librarians' superior behavioral performance is likely to foster greater student e-loyalty to library services. Student e-loyalty reflects the perceived benefits and rewards students derive from using web-based library services, including satisfaction, perceived usefulness, convenience, and overall positive experiences. Previous research (Kim et al., 2009; Suhartanto et al., 2018) affirmed that loyal customers are more inclined to make repeat purchases compared to new customers, thereby, emphasizing the importance of delivering high-quality services to cultivate customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are directly correlated, as Kiran (2011) noted in her work on the investigation of the antecedents of customer loyalty in an academic library setting. Thus, e-loyalty among library users is sought because dedicated patrons often leave positive feedback and recommendations about the library.

Further, the increase of positive feedback and recommendations about the library would also mean an increased patronage and usage. In this context, students' E-loyalty represents users' commitment, higher expectations, satisfaction and loyalty to the digital library platform, their inclination to return for future interactions, and their propensity to recommend the platform to others. Hence, the interconnected relationship between quality web-based services, librarians' behavioral performance, and students' e-loyalty is considered as the basis for developing best practices offered to students and the community in Northern Mindanao libraries. The concept of e-service quality has emerged as a significant factor in meeting the demands of online users and enhancing e-loyalty (Langer, 2018).

With the theory and concepts cited, this provides a lens to understand the dynamics of the quality of web-based library services, librarians' behavioral performance and e-loyalty in web-based library service contexts. It underscores the importance of creating equitable and satisfying experiences for students engaging with digital library services. Thus, the researcher intends to explore the correlation between the quality of web-based library service, librarians' behavioral performance, and its implication towards students' e-loyalty. Figure 1 shows the interplay of the variables in the study, wherein the quality of web-based library services and librarians' behavioral performance are assumed to influence e-loyalty.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Study

Research Questions

This study determined the exploration of the connection of quality of web-based library service, librarians' behavioral performance, and student E-loyalty. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What participants assessment of the quality of web-based library service considering the following: environmental factors; delivery factors; and outcome factors
- (2) What is the librarians' level of behavioral performance as assessed by the students in terms of the following dimensions: inclusion; approachability; engagement; searching; evaluation; and closure
- (3) What is the extent of the participants' e-loyalty to their school's web-based library services
- (4) Do the students' assessment of the quality of web-based library service and the librarians' level of behavioral performance significantly influence their e-loyalty?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive correlational research design to determine the quality of web-based library services and librarians' behavioral performance and its influence on students' e-loyalty. A random sampling using the Yammane formula to get the desired sample size was used. This study was participated by six hundred fifty-seven (657) participants from different schools in Northern Mindanao.

The researcher adapted and modified the first part of the survey instrument which was taken from the Library Website Satisfaction questionnaire of Kiran and Diljit (2012) to describe the participants' assessment of the quality of web-based library service in terms of environmental factors, delivery factors, and outcome factors. The second part of the survey instrument was based on the Reference and User Services Association (2023) that determined the participants' assessment of the librarians' level of behavioral performance as assessed by the students in terms of the following dimensions such as inclusion, approachability, engagement, searching, evaluation, and Closure. The third part of the survey instrument based from Srinivasan et al. (2002), Zeithaml et al. (1996) was adapted and modified to evaluate the participants' assessment of the participants' level of e-loyalty to their school's web-based library services.

For the statistical treatment of data, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviations were used for problems 1, 2 and 3. For problem 4, regression analysis was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the summary table of the graduate students' assessment on the quality of web-based library services. Findings revealed that quality of web-based library services is rated generally as Very Satisfactory as indicated in the overall mean (M=4.12). The participants rated the quality of web-based library service as Very Satisfactory with delivery factors (M=4.15) which has the highest mean, followed by environmental factors (M=4.13), and outcome factors (4.08). The very satisfactory rating for delivery factors

indicates that the participants found the service well-designed and efficient. They appreciated the ease of navigation, various options, and responsiveness of the system. The availability of communication channels also likely played a significant role, indicating that participants felt supported and able to seek help when needed. Environmental factors, including internet connectivity, ease of use, access to resources, and overall user-friendliness, were also rated very satisfactory.

Delivery factors encompass the components and attributes that users perceive as being user-friendly when accessing materials and services through online library platforms. This implies that while participants assessed the web-based library services, they placed a high value on factors connected to service delivery, such as efficiency, dependability, and convenience. Opoko and Kwaku (2022) affirmed that perceived ease of use on online resources, and simplicity of use, task functionality, and service functionality are some of the delivery characteristics that affect web-based library services.

Table 1

Summary Table of the Quality of Web-based Library Service

Factors	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Environmental Factors	4.13	High	0.39
Delivery Factors	4.15	High	0.44
Outcome Factors	4.08	High	0.43
Grand Mean	4.12	High	0.37

The mean ranges for the factors are as follows: environmental factors have a mean range of 0.095, delivery factors have a mean range of 0.05, and outcome factors have a mean range of 0.05. These values suggest that environmental factors exhibit the highest variability, followed by delivery factors and then outcome factors, with the latter two showing similar moderate levels of variability.

Environmental factors are factors affecting the online library service's virtual environment particularly on the access to the internet, usability, availability of digital materials, and the general friendliness of the service for library patrons. A study by Kato (2021) emphasized that environmental factors affecting web-based library service include ease of use, accessibility, simple interface design, excellent communication quality, Internet performance, performance assurance services, social network communication ease, and customer-driven acquisition. Thus, it is considered as a critical factor due to these significant web-based library service features that it brings to the virtual environment.

Furthermore, outcome factors pertaining to the efficiency of the library in fulfilling the information demands of its patrons include the delivery of up-to-date and extensive content as well as the prompt response of librarians via virtual reference chat assistance. This suggests that meeting students' academic needs and raising their level of satisfaction with web-based library services depends on the accessibility and

dependability of these services such as enhanced learning outcomes, easier access to relevant material, and academic success loyalty (Prihanto & Mohammad, 2023).

Table 2

Summary Table of Behavioral Performance as Assessed by the Participants

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Inclusion	4.17	High	0.43
Approachability	4.16	High	0.43
Engagement	4.15	High	0.46
Searching	4.14	High	0.45
Evaluation	4.16	High	0.45
Closure	4.15	High	0.47
Grand Mean	4.15	High	0.39

Table 2 presents the summary table of the librarians' behavioral performance as assessed by the participants in terms of inclusion, approachability, engagement, searching, evaluation, and closure. Findings showed that librarians are inclusive, reliable, engaging, comprehensive in their information search and assessment, and efficient in closing deals as revealed in the overall mean of 4.15. This finding is supported by Trott and Schwartz (2014) who both confirmed the significance of a librarian's behavioral performance, especially during reference interviews, which requires a flexible and continuously evolving skill set to understand and effectively cater to users' information requirements

Remarkably, all dimensions of behavioral performance were rated "high" by the participants. The dimension that received the highest rating is the inclusion (M=4.17) rated as "high". This implies that the quality of behavioral performance manifested by librarians during reference interviews would mean that they are warmly catering all types of participants with high respect, fair treatment, opportunities regardless of diverse culture and personal traits of participants. This is in consonance with the RUSA Guidelines for Behavioral Performance of Reference and Information Service Providers (2023) that good behaviors of librarians such as, inclusion, approachability, searching, engagement, evaluation, and closure are to be manifested to successfully provide quality information services to participants.

The second behavioral performance of librarian indicators that were rated as "high" by the participants are approachability and evaluation (M=4.16). This means that during the virtual transactions, participants perceived librarians as welcoming, open-minded, approachable, and friendly. The librarian also likely offered search strategies, direct instructions, follow-up, and feedback before ending the interview. Evidently, librarians

exhibited excellent customer service by extending warm greetings at the beginning of engagements and closings following transactions during virtual reference interview support (Lux & Rich, 2016). They also assisted users with evaluating search results to ensure that they are suitable for their reading level, language, and format. They also guided consumers to additional resources if necessary.

Table 3

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Web-Based Library Service and the Librarians' Behavioral Performance on their E-Loyalty

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.506	.152		3.34	.001
Quality of Web-Based Library Service	.266	.058	.211	4.57**	.000
Librarians' Behavioral Performance	.616	.055	.516	11.19**	.000

Model Summary

R = .695 R² = .482 Adjusted R² = .481 F = 304.88** p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level

Table 3 presents the regression analysis of the influence of the participants' assessment of the quality of web-based library service and the librarians' behavioral performance on their e-loyalty. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant (F=304.88, p =.000). Furthermore, 48.2 percent of the variability in their e-loyalty can be accounted for by a combination of their assessment of the quality of web-based library service and librarian's behavioral performance. The remaining 61.8 percent can be attributed to other factors not covered in this study such as e-trust, e-satisfaction, and electronic word of mouth marketing and continuance intention. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Participants who are very satisfied to the quality of web-based library service and high level of librarians' behavioral performance are having higher levels of e-loyalty. This indicates that the participants who have a very satisfactory experience of the quality of web-based library service in terms of environmental factors, delivery factors and outcome factors also tend to use the library more often. This suggests that users are more likely to become loyal to a web-based library service if they believe it offers high-quality services and has beneficial interactions with librarians. Thus, e-loyalty could show up in several ways, such as continuing to use the service, telling others about it, or speaking well about it. With the use of this information, libraries and librarians may improve user interactions and service quality, which will increase graduate student engagement and E-loyalty.

For instance, participants had a wonderful experience on web-based library services in terms of easier navigation to the web-based library in finding relevant, reliable resources with strong search capabilities; accessed seamlessly anytime and anywhere;

has an impressive quality of well-designed interface, easy to navigate; demonstrates high quality of meeting users' information needs, by providing up-to-date and comprehensive content, and timely response of the librarians to the library users. Smith et al. (2018) provided evidence for this, showing that students' perceptions of accessibility, usability, and responsiveness have a major influence on how satisfied they are with online library services. Indeed, Tan (2019) highlighted that a visually appealing and user-friendly web-based library interface positively affects student engagement and e-loyalty. Sahu (2007) asserted that if a library delivers accurate information to the correct user within an appropriate framework and in a timely manner, it can be deemed as offering high-quality service to its users. This study is supported by Adayi (2023) highlighting that the efficient and timely delivery of information becomes a key driver in enhancing student e-loyalty. Similarly, Dalbehera (2020) and Moses et al., (2016) opined that understanding and enhancing the quality of web-based library services positively impacts user satisfaction and e-loyalty.

Furthermore, during virtual reference transactions, the participants experienced a high level of treatment in terms of inclusion, approachability, engagement, searching, evaluation, and closure that contributed to the level of students' e-loyalty to school web-based. For instance, librarians ensured that the services and resources are welcoming and accessible to all members of the community regardless of cultural diversity and economic status. Likewise, in virtual or online settings, librarians' exceptional level of approachability is evident. This suggests that participants valued engagement, especially when it comes to online chat, where librarians must firmly commit to providing helpful information support.

In addition, librarians are knowledgeable about search strategies and they clarify steps for patrons while respecting their time constraints. Similarly, librarians as experts in evaluating the quality of information considered factors like accuracy, authority, bias, comprehensiveness, and coverage in the evaluative process. Indeed, participants also experienced how librarians manifested valuable means of bringing conversations in a meaningful manner with concise instructions and answers. Similarly, Li et al. (2019) underscored the importance of librarian engagement and responsiveness in various communication channels in enhancing user satisfaction and fostering e-loyalty. In addition, Mawhinney's (2020) insight on the importance of personalness and informality further enhances user experiences in utilizing virtual reference services, emphasizing the positive impact of librarian's behavioral performance

As such, the more the participants experienced high quality web-based library service and high quality of librarians' behavioral performance, the higher their e-loyalty to the school's web-based library services. This result found that patron's satisfaction and user's loyalty are influenced by library service quality factors (Twum et al., 2022).

Conclusions

The web-based library services provided by libraries ensure the continued and uninterrupted access to the library's resources and services. The librarians demonstrate faithfulness in implementing the Guidelines for Behavioral Performance of Reference and Information Service Providers in attending to the information needs of the graduate students. Evidently, the quality of web-based library services and the librarians' behavioral performance significantly affect the graduate students' e-loyalty. The results of this investigation support the assertions of Adam's Equity Theory (1963) that the quality of web-based library service and librarians' positive behavior contribute to students' e-loyalty. A web-based library service that is well designed with advanced functionality, friendly graphical user interface, accessible, ease of use, up-to-date, reliable, timely in giving responses to users helps boost users' preferences and increase e-loyalty to students.

In a nutshell, the advancement of continuous development, librarians' training in digital literacy, behavioral performance competencies and skills, tailored recommendations, efficient communication, and promptness are emphasized as strategies for fostering increasing student e-loyalty.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were drawn by the Researcher:

- (1) That school administrators may consider enhancing the service's design and functionality to maintain user-friendliness and efficiency, providing more options to cater to diverse needs, ensuring the system remains reliable during peak times, and regularly gathering user feedback for continuous improvement.
- (2) Librarians may consider engaging in the continuous development of educational programs on technological advancement, attending seminars and workshops to enhance knowledge and competencies in web-based library services. They may also consider effective utilization of school web-based libraries by ensuring they meet or exceed student expectations with relevant, up-to-date, and user-friendly resources, and by encouraging students to use the web-based libraries regularly and recommend them to others. (
- 3) That future researchers may consider exploring other variables related to the quality of web-based library services that could potentially influence school web-based E-loyalty of students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before determining the number of participants for the study, the researcher submitted a consent form to the graduate school office. The researcher sought the approval of the school's Research Ethics Committee (REC) to ensure that the study follows the ethical guidelines of this research undertaking as it involved human participants. The researcher followed all the ethical and legal procedures when conducting the interview. Participants were informed by presenting the permission letter for their voluntary participation and informed consent. The participants' identities in the study were not exposed, and the confidentiality and privacy of their identities were maintained to avoid conflicts. The participants' participation in the study served as baseline data for recommendations in the administration to improve the school's web-based library services, ultimately enhancing every student's educational experience. To respect participant autonomy, participants could skip any question they did not wish to answer and proceed to the next one. The researcher guaranteed that the participant's consent to participate in the study was secure and safe. Furthermore, the participants were assured that their comments would be kept confidential. All the information that they provided was recognized and presented accurately. The researcher incorporated the principles and ethical considerations outlined in the research conducted by Alvarado & Sebial (2023).

With all these ethical considerations and after the approval of REC, the researcher sent a letter of request to the respective libraries in Northern Mindanao through email. The approval letter from REC was attached and presented to the College of Graduate Study to start the administration of the questionnaire. The duration of the study started from February-April 2024. The participants were expected to participate in the data collection starting February 28, 2024, until March 28, 2024.

The data-gathering procedure involved the use of an online survey that was sent to the selected participants via email. The survey was designed to collect information on the participants' e-loyalty with their school's web-based library service. To minimize misunderstanding, the goal of the study as well as the instructions was stated in the Google form survey questionnaire before the participants filled out the form. Moreover, after all of the questions were sought and answered, the completed questionnaires were then retrieved and statistically processed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Acknowledgments

In this arduous journey, the researcher would like to extend her deepest gratitude to Lourdes College Graduate School, to her adviser, Dr. Melody R. Agcito, for her adviser and the cornerstone of this endeavor, her unwavering mentorship, expertise, patience, and encouragement. The researcher also grateful to the panel members, for their valuable suggestions, inspiring motivation, and expert guidance to enhance this study. To her parents, from whom she found strength and inspiration.

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